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Research article

Shift in habitat selection during natal dispersal in a long-lived raptor species

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Animals select their habitat along environmental gradients, but the mechanisms that constrain the ecological requirements of an individual can differ between life stages. Dispersal is a key demographic process that determines gene flow and alters species distributions, yet few empirical studies have examined whether habitat selection in animals is changing during dispersal. In this study, we examined changes in habitat preferences during natal dispersal of red kites *Milvus milvus*, a European raptor species. By deploying solar-powered GPS-GSM transmitters on nestlings, we continuously tracked individuals up to six years (2015–2020), from fledging to settlement. We applied habitat selection functions (HSF) to the tracking data using hierarchical generalized additive models, a flexible method which combines individual- and population-level inference, while allowing for the contrast of the prospecting and settlement phases. During the prospecting phase ($n=204$ birds), individuals were less responsive to their environment than during the settlement phase, resulting in a predicted wide distribution in western Europe. During the settlement phase, individuals ($n=78$ birds) selected a narrower range of environmental gradients, while avoiding areas of high elevation, steep topographic slopes, high human population density and highly heterogeneous landscapes. During this phase, individuals were also more philopatric, i.e. they were more inclined to choose an environment closer to their natal area, than during the prospecting phase. Suitable habitats predicted during settlement were much more spatially contrasted than during prospecting. Our study provides empirical evidence that habitat selection changes across natal dispersal phases in a long-lived species, indicating that species conservation strategies should account for different environmental constraints before and after settlement. Furthermore, our findings underscore the importance of long-term tracking data, with sufficient sample size, to study the link between habitat selection and natal dispersal.

Keywords: biologging, habitat selection, movement ecology, ontogeny, resource selection function, species distribution model

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Introduction

The study of habitat selection is critical to the understanding of how individuals interact with their environment and generate population-level distribution and abundance patterns (Boyce and McDonald 1999, Matthiopoulos et al. 2015, Northrup et al. 2022). Animals are constantly moving during their life cycle and therefore different life stages may exhibit different habitat preferences leading to stage-specific spatial distribution (Turchin 1998, Fortin 2020, Veech 2021). However, only a few studies of long-lived species have investigated differences in habitat selection between life stages (Kays et al. 2015, but see Killeen et al. 2014, O'Neill et al. 2020, Vignali et al. 2021, Frankish et al. 2022, Thorsen et al. 2022), although it has been recognized that ignoring stage-dependence in habitat selection can lead to unrealistic inference of species distribution and biased management recommendations (McLoughlin et al. 2010, Hooten et al. 2017, Northrup et al. 2022).

Understanding how habitat preferences differ between life stages should become increasingly possible with recent advances in tracking technologies (Hazen et al. 2012, Kays et al. 2015, Spiegel et al. 2017, Nathan et al. 2022). By extending the monitoring duration, these technologies now make it possible to study habitat selection throughout the dispersal process, which was known to be particularly difficult to track (Jönsson et al. 2016, Hooten et al. 2017). Though many species show specific movement behaviours before their first reproduction, little is known about habitat selection during the pre-reproductive stage of animals (Penteriani and Delgado 2009, Hazen et al. 2012, Kays et al. 2015, Serrano et al. 2018, Veech 2021).

Dispersing prior to the first breeding event (i.e. natal dispersal) is, in many species, more common and generally occurs over greater distances than breeding dispersal (between two breeding events, Greenwood and Harvey 1982, Paradis et al. 1998, Harts et al. 2016). Natal dispersal has therefore the largest impact on both individual fitness and population structure (Matthysen 2012). During natal dispersal, immatures (i.e. individuals from independence to first reproduction) typically perform explorative movements during which they can assess the quality of habitats encountered (Reed 1999, Debeffe et al. 2013, Ponchon et al. 2013). This information gathered might then be used for subsequent habitat choices during future settlement (Doligez and Boulinier 2008).

Classical habitat selection theory assumes that individuals should select habitats that maximize their fitness (Fretwell and Lucas 1969, Wiens 1976), which implies that individuals should have perfect knowledge of their environment. However, during natal dispersal, immatures are lacking the experience and/or time to assess the quality of new habitats encountered (Stamps et al. 2005). Habitat selection during natal dispersal can therefore be viewed as a developmental continuum, beginning early in life, developing during dispersal movements, and continuing even when dispersers decide to settle in a breeding habitat (Reed 1999, Stamps

2001, Doligez and Boulinier 2008). Movements of dispersers can thus be divided into two phases (following Delgado and Penteriani 2008, Delgado et al. 2009, 2010): a wandering phase (hereafter 'prospecting phase') and a successive, more stationary phase at a potential new breeding site (hereafter 'settlement phase').

Some empirical studies have described marked behavioural differences between these two dispersal phases. For example, prospecting guineafowls, owls and lions move faster and straighter during the prospecting phase (Delgado et al. 2009, Elliott et al. 2014, Klarevas-Irby et al. 2021); however, how habitat selection is changing between prospecting and the subsequent settlement period is still poorly investigated. Like prospectors, individuals during the settlement period should be constrained by the availability of suitable food sources, but also by the availability of other resources necessary for successful breeding, such as breeding sites, mating partners or additional ecological requirements (Doligez and Boulinier 2008). Thus, it is expected that prospectors would have a more flexible habitat selection than settlers and, conversely, habitat selection should change as individuals become more selective during settlement.

Some of the most important environmental gradients that strongly influence species distribution include the amount of available habitat, elevation and human population density (Isbell et al. 2022). For example, habitat selection changed along longitudinal and latitudinal gradients of boreal forests in caribou during winter (Fortin et al. 2008), along elevation gradients in owls (Kramer et al. 2021) or urbanization gradients in lions and bears (Benson et al. 2016, Thorsen et al. 2022). Assessing habitat selection along environmental gradients could therefore help evaluate how changes in habitat availability and quality may influence current and future population distributions (Hargreaves and Eckert 2014, Matthiopoulos et al. 2015, Anderson et al. 2022).

Prospecting allows individuals to gather crucial information about how habitat quality is changing along environmental gradients (Ponchon et al. 2013), and the decision to settle will largely influence the lifetime fitness of individuals (Delgado et al. 2014, Oro et al. 2021, Ponchon and Travis 2022). The prospecting and settlement phases are therefore crucial because they are likely to strongly influence population distribution and dynamics, through colonization processes and range expansion (Bowler and Benton 2005, Kokko and López-Sepulcre 2006, Clobert et al. 2009, Oro et al. 2021, Ponchon and Travis 2022).

In this study, we applied habitat selection functions (HSF, also called resource selection functions, reviewed by Northrup et al. 2022) to a telemetry dataset of immature red kites *Milvus milvus* originating from Switzerland. This species is native to the European continent and often shows philopatric recruitment behaviour despite long migratory and prospecting movements spanning various European regions (Literák et al. 2022, Mattsson et al. 2022). Migration routes are variable, with some individuals undertaking longer routes, while others prefer to stay closer to their birthplace. All juvenile individuals leave the parental home range

(Scherler et al. 2023) and express prospecting behaviour during the transience phase of natal dispersal to find a suitable first breeding territory to settle (Bowler and Benton 2005, Clobert et al. 2012). However, the extent to which the distance of the movements from the natal nest shapes the habitat preference remains a question that warrants further investigation. This study aims to delve also into this aspect, looking at differences in habitat selection between prospecting and settlement phases of natal dispersal, while considering the potential influence of the distance from the natal nest on habitat selection.

This raptor species is particularly suitable to study for habitat selection during natal dispersal because it is long-lived (up to 30 years in the wild, Bird et al. 2020) while attaining sexual maturity predominantly at only two years of age (Katzenberger et al. 2021). This relatively early maturity eases the study of movement drivers, both during prospecting and settlement phases of natal dispersal. After fledging, juvenile red kites spend some time prospecting before beginning their first winter migration, but most of the prospecting occurs after the return of winter migrations and may be repeated for several years before settlement (Aebischer and Scherler 2021). In recent years, there have been increasing reports of red kites being sighted at higher elevations and within urban environments (Knaus et al. 2018). This emerging trend raises questions about the factors influencing habitat selection in these specific habitats, which is especially significant in the context of ongoing environmental changes (Mattsson et al. 2022).

By using solar-powered GPS-GSM transmitters, we were able to continuously track immatures up to six years and to compare habitat selection during the prospecting and the successive settlement phase of natal dispersal. We analysed the movement data of immature red kites 1) to investigate population-level habitat associations and potential changes in habitat preferences along two key environmental gradients (elevation and human population density), and between the two dispersal phases, while accounting for the distance to the natal site; and 2) to estimate predicted distribution of relative probabilities of occurrence for the two dispersal phases.

Because immatures during the prospecting phase should move continuously to explore new areas and sample different habitat patches, we expect habitat selection to be less pronounced during the prospecting phase than during the settlement phase. Based on typical dispersal patterns (Nathan et al. 2012), we expect settlers to exhibit higher degrees of philopatry, suggesting that they may be less likely to settle far from their natal sites compared to the distribution range observed in prospectors. This difference in responsiveness to habitat characteristics between the two phases should result in a more contrasted distribution of occurrence probability during settlement than during prospecting. The study will provide a better understanding of the possible underlying mechanisms of ontogenetic changes in habitat selection that are expected to occur during natal dispersal in most long-lived species.

Material and methods

Study species

The red kite is a partially migrating raptor that occurs almost exclusively in the southern and temperate regions of Europe, with most populations migrating south in winter (Mattsson et al. 2022). Red kites generally breed in small forest patches situated in heterogeneous agricultural landscapes (Hothorn et al. 2011, Heuck et al. 2013, Carter and Powell 2019), usually associated with medium–low elevations (Seoane et al. 2003, Sergio et al. 2005). Red kites forage opportunistically, usually in open farmland habitats, by hunting prey or scavenging remains associated with agricultural landscapes. Red kites also use urban areas which provide additional food resources such as carcasses, food waste or compost (Welti et al. 2020). Like many raptors, red kites were persecuted by humans until the first half of the 20th century, resulting in a sharp decline in population size and a contraction of the distributional range all over Europe (Mattsson et al. 2022). Since the implementation of raptor protection laws, most of the populations have shown signs of recovery (Mattsson et al. 2022), particularly in Switzerland where the population has continued to grow and expand its range over past decades (Knaus et al. 2018).

Study area and tagging

Fieldwork was conducted in western Switzerland in a study area of ca 400 km² within the cantons of Bern and Fribourg from 2015 to 2020. The study area hosts approximately 130 red kite breeding pairs per year (Nägeli et al. 2022), representing a high breeding density compared to other breeding areas in Europe (Aebischer and Scherler 2021). During the six years of monitoring a total of 204 nestlings (detailed sample sizes in Supporting information) was equipped with solar powered GPS Global System for Mobile communications – Ultra High Frequency (GPS GSM-UHF) transmitters (Ecotone SKUA/CREX type or Milsar M9 GPS GSM-UHF type). Transmitters were deployed at a nestling age of ca 40 days and fitted by using a backpack style diagonal loop (details of the deployments protocol are in Scherler et al. 2023). GPS transmitters were set to collect positions at 1 h for the Ecotone tags and 10 min intervals for the Milsar tags. All data were transmitted via GSM and automatically stored on the Movebank data repository (movebank.org).

Data preparation

All data were processed and analysed using R software (R ver. 4.2.2, www.r-project.org).

Tracks segmentation and formatting

In this study, our primary interest lay in the habitat selection of red kites during dispersal phases. Therefore, our initial goal was to discern and exclude migration and overwintering trajectories from our analysis. However, distinguishing

prospecting movements from migration can present a challenge, particularly in juveniles and immatures, known for their vagrant behaviour (Scherler 2020). To separate the migration from prospecting movement, we therefore performed track segmentation by using a recently developed segmentation-clustering approach (R package 'seglust2d', Patin et al. 2020). By using the Lavielle method adapted to handle two-dimensional data (Patin et al. 2020), segmentation for each individual track was done based on the time series of GPS locations (longitude and latitude). This method detects change points in a time series and separates different spatiotemporal units corresponding to distinct ranges, thereby allowing us to distinguish the migration phase from the dispersal phase. For each individual, we visually assessed the quality of the segmentation using net squared displacement plots (Bunnfeld et al. 2011, Supporting information).

In certain cases, the algorithm flagged the beginning of prospecting movements at locations notably distant from the birds' birthplace upon their return from migration. We acknowledged the likely interrelation between migration and prospecting behaviours, and hence opted for a cautious strategy. Rather than omitting these data points, we chose to incorporate them into our analysis, as they offer a deeper understanding of the complex movements of these immature red kites. In the following analyses, the overwintering and migration phases were therefore excluded, and the remaining tracks were separated per calendar year, for each individual (Supporting information). Erroneous locations were then identified and removed using a speed filter of 35 ms^{-1} (R package 'argosfilter', Freitas et al. 2008). Finally, tracks were resampled into a continuous series of 1 h movements across each individual (R package 'amt', Signer et al. 2018).

Available locations

After excluding wintering and migration, we calculated the yearly home range for each individual, using a 100% minimum convex polygon (MCP, R package 'amt', Signer et al. 2018) around all GPS fixes. Assuming that the accessible space for prospecting and settlement was restricted for each kite to their yearly MCP, available locations were randomly sampled for each individual, within each corresponding yearly MCP, using a 1:1 ratio of used versus available points (Supporting information). Following Fithian and Hastie (2013), a weight of 5000 was assigned to every available point and a weight of one for every presence point. The final dataset included a total of 4.2 million locations (presence and available locations) for a total of 745 individual kite-years (details in Supporting information).

Prospecting versus settlement phases

During the breeding season (March–August), GPS tracks of all birds were regularly checked. When birds showed restricted movements, they were observed in the field within 14 days, to visually verify whether they had established a territory. Observations of an individual with a partner, as well as indications for nest building, breeding attempts or defensive behaviour within the suspected home range, were strong

evidence of territory establishment. We therefore defined a settlement event as when an individual has its first territory. Individual kite-years were then divided into two different groups: prospectors (pre-settlement phase, $n=204$ unique individuals, corresponding to 615 kite-years, Supporting information) and settlers (after they had their first territory, $n=78$ unique individuals, corresponding to 130 kite-years, Supporting information). For the scope of this study, we thus defined the prospecting phase as the period between winter migrations and before immatures establish their first territory, whereas we defined the settlement phase as the period after immatures have established their first territory (following Delgado and Penteriani 2008, Delgado et al. 2009).

Environmental covariates

Based on previous work on red kites (Hothorn et al. 2011, Heuck et al. 2013) we selected the following categorical and continuous environmental covariates to extract the environmental information at presence and available points (spatial and temporal resolutions with references of covariates given in Supporting information). Corine land cover (CLC) data were used to identify locations at six different categorical habitat classes: forest, pastures, arable fields, urban (including cities and villages) and wetlands (including marshes, rivers and lakes). These classes represent the most important habitats encountered by red kites (Supporting information), so the remaining classes were grouped into a generic class named 'others' (mainly heterogeneous agricultural areas and shrub areas). Five continuous covariates were included: two variables of topography (elevation and slope), human population density, forest density (level of tree cover density in a range from 0% to 100%) and, to account for philopatric behaviour, distance to the natal nest. A landscape heterogeneity index based on the six CLC classes was calculated within a 2 km radius buffer (which is the average size of a territory, Scherler et al. 2023), for each presence and available location. This heterogeneity index (also called 'patch density', which is the ratio of the number of habitat patches divided by the area considered, see McGarigal 1995) was calculated using the R package 'landscapemetrics' (Hesselbarth et al. 2019). The heterogeneity index starts from 0 (only a single patch in the surrounding landscape) and increases as the landscape gets patchier (increase in heterogeneity; McGarigal 1995, Supporting information). For each presence and available point, land cover classes, elevation, topographic slope, human population, forest density and heterogeneity index were extracted using the R package 'amt' (Signer et al. 2018). We tested for collinearity among continuous covariates using Pearson correlation coefficient and variation inflation factor (VIF). Correlation coefficients were ≤ 0.7 (Dormann et al. 2012) and VIFs ≤ 3 (Zuur et al. 2009), so all continuous covariates were retained for the following analyses.

Habitat selection functions

Using presence (1) and available (0) locations as response variables, we fitted HSF (Boyce and McDonald 1999,

Manly et al. 2007, Fieberg et al. 2021) at a third-order scale (within home ranges, Johnson 1980) to estimate the relative selection strength, as a function of the six environmental covariates (CLC classes, elevation, slope, human population density, forest density and heterogeneity index). Separate HSF were run for prospectors and settlers. To allow for non-linear relationships we used hierarchical generalized additive models (HGAM, Aarts et al. 2008, Pedersen et al. 2019) using the 'mgcv' R package (Wood et al. 2017) with a binomial distribution and a complementary log–log link function (McCabe et al. 2021). All covariate smoothers were implemented using thin plate regression splines with shrinkage to prevent overfitting (Wood et al. 2017). The CLC covariate was added as a parametric term and as an interaction (using the 'by=' argument) with elevation and human population density covariates. We acknowledge that the CLC data used may have limitations in accuracy, particularly in Mediterranean landscapes and at the finest scales (Bachantourian et al. 2022). However, we used a broader scale (level 2), and any potential inaccuracies would affect both prospectors and settlers similarly, maintaining the validity of our comparisons. In order to account for the hierarchical structure of the data and to control for individual variation, the identifiers corresponding to each individual kite-year were fit as random 'slope|intercept' effects (Muff et al. 2020, McCabe et al. 2021). To limit residual autocorrelation, a temporal autoregressive correlation structure of order 1 (CorAR1) was implemented (Beale et al. 2010, Wood 2017). Finally, we also added an additional smoother – a two-dimensional spline on geographical coordinates, to take into account the spatial structure of the data (Beale et al. 2010, Hefley et al. 2017). We evaluated each model using fivefold cross-validation, blocked by individuals (Roberts et al. 2017). Individual data were split randomly with 80% of the data to fit the HSF and 20% to test it. The corresponding output was based on the Spearman's rank correlation (Boyce et al. 2002) and varied between 0 (low predictive performance) and 1 (good predictive performance). All models performed well (0.97 ± 0.03 , Supporting information).

Relative occurrence probability

Habitat preferences $w(x)$ were finally estimated with the following equations (see details in Aarts et al. 2008, Hooten et al. 2017, Fieberg et al. 2021) for the prospectors and settlers separately:

$$w(x) = \exp(b_0 + s(x_1) + \dots + s(x_k)) \quad (1)$$

with b_0 being the model intercept (which only represents the ratio of presence versus available locations when all other covariates were set to 0, see explanations in Muff et al. 2020, Fieberg et al. 2021) and $s(x_{1..k})$ being the smoothers for each covariate. For mapping, the relative usage values W for each used and available cell were then calculated with:

$$W = w(x) / \text{sum}(w(x)) \quad (2)$$

that we converted in a relative probability of occurrence p by using the following transformation (Johnson et al. 2004):

$$p = (W - W_{\min}) / (W_{\max} - W_{\min}) \quad (3)$$

Sample representativeness

To assess the adequacy of our sample sizes on the estimation of population distribution range using MCPs from tracked individuals, we calculated 'representative values' from saturation curves (Beal et al. 2021) for both phases, prospecting and settlement. We randomly and iteratively selected an increasing number of individuals' MCP, and at each step we calculated the mean and standard deviation of the proportion of locations falling into MCPs over the total number of locations. For both stages, we obtained values $> 97\%$, which indicated that our sample size was sufficiently representative of the population distribution during both stages (Beal et al. 2021, Supporting information). We conducted an additional analysis to address potential issues due to sample size differences between prospectors ($n=204$) and settlers ($n=78$). Given that all settlers were also part of the prospectors group, we downsized the prospectors group to match the number of individuals in the settlers group ($n=78$). This step ensured that our results were not skewed due to sample size discrepancies (Supporting information).

Age effect

Finally, we also aimed to disentangle the effects of changes between the natal dispersal phases (prospecting to settlement) from the influence of age and experience. To achieve this, we ran HSF for each age class (1, 2, 3+) during the prospecting phase. This analysis was specifically performed on a subset of individuals ($n=78$) that experienced both prospecting and settlement phases. By examining prospectors and settlers within the same age class, we gained insights into age-related changes in habitat selection and were able to distinguish them from changes between the two dispersal phases.

Results

Habitats preferences

In both the prospecting and the settlement phase, arable fields and forested areas were the only habitat classes selected compared to their availability, whereas only wetlands were avoided (Supporting information). However, the relative selection strength for each land cover class was dependent on both elevation and human population density, and differed between the two phases (Fig. 1, 2). During the prospecting phase, individuals generally used a wider range of elevation and human population densities (Fig. 1). Landcover preferences of prospectors shifted marginally along the elevational

Figure 1. Estimates of relative selection for six Corine land cover (CLC) classes as a function of elevation encountered by immature red kites during natal dispersal: partial effects reflect how a given habitat is used (> 0) or avoided (< 0) relative to its availability (Avgar et al. 2017, Fieberg et al. 2021). Prospecting red kites (orange, $n = 204$ birds) show a stronger change of habitat selection with elevation than during the settlement phase (green, $n = 78$ birds). Summaries of the model outputs are provided in the Supporting information.

gradient: only forest and grassland areas were slightly preferred at medium elevation (800–1200 m) and arable fields avoided at low but not at high elevations, Fig. 1). The class ‘others’ was only avoided at high elevation (> 2000 m), which in this case corresponded mainly to heterogeneous agricultural areas and shrub areas.

During the settlement phase, however, response curves were more pronounced, with a marked optimal elevation range for arable, forest and grasslands of about 800–900 m. High elevations (> 1000 m) were strongly avoided, especially for forest, grassland areas and the ‘others’ class (Fig. 1). Urban areas were avoided at low elevations (< 1000 m) and

Figure 2. Estimates of relative selection for six Corine land cover (CLC) classes as a function of human population density encountered by immature red kites during natal dispersal: partial effects reflect how a given habitat is used (> 0) or avoided (< 0) relative to its availability (Avgar et al. 2017, Fieberg et al. 2021). Prospecting red kites (orange, $n = 204$ birds) show a stronger change of habitat selection with human population density than during the settlement phase (green, $n = 78$ birds). Summaries of the model outputs are provided in the Supporting information.

selected at high elevation (> 1000 m, Fig. 1). For all habitat classes except urban and wetlands during prospecting, relative selection strength decreased as human population density increased, but the relationships were more pronounced during the settlement phase than during the prospecting phase (Fig. 2).

Steep topographic slopes were also more strongly avoided during the settlement phase than during the prospecting phase (Fig. 3). A medium range of forest density was selected, but only during the settlement phase (Fig. 3). Habitat heterogeneity did not greatly influence selection during the prospecting phase, but highly heterogeneous areas were avoided during the settlement phase (Fig. 3). Finally, for both phases, there was a strong preference for locations near to the natal nest, but the relationship was also more pronounced during the settlement phase (Fig. 3).

Age effect

The habitat selection curves for dispersing red kites showed consistent trends across different age classes and dispersal phases (Supporting information). Red kites generally avoided higher elevations, with this preference slightly intensifying with age during prospecting but becoming much more pronounced at the change from prospecting to settlement within the same 3+ age class (Supporting information). Red kites favoured areas with low densities of human population, a preference that also considerably increased when changing from the prospecting to the settlement phase within the same age class (Supporting information).

Relative probability of occurrence

The analysis of predictive maps for dispersing red kites revealed distinct differences in the probability of occurrence between the prospecting and settlement phases (Fig. 4). During the prospecting phase, the average probability of occurrence was high and evenly distributed, with 22% of the cells exhibiting a suitable probability ($p > 0.75$, Supporting information). Areas that were clearly avoided, such as high elevation areas in the Alps, lakes or large cities, represented only 3.5% of the cells with a probability below 0.5 (Supporting information). High occurrence probability areas during this phase were predominantly located in Switzerland and southern Germany (Fig. 4). During the settlement phase, the distribution of occurrence probability was much more contrasted (with probabilities ranging from high to low values, Supporting information). Although a similar proportion of cells displayed high occurrence (19.8% with a suitable probability, $p > 0.75$, Supporting information), the proportion of low occurrence cells increased substantially to 28.1% ($p < 0.5$, Supporting information). The avoided areas in this phase were primarily situated on the periphery of the distribution, specifically in the Massif Central region in France and northern Germany (Fig. 4). High occurrence probability areas were still primarily found in the Swiss plateau and Alpine valleys but were also notably concentrated in southern Germany (Fig. 4).

Discussion

Using a large dataset of telemetry locations and a flexible analytical method of habitat selection that allows for

Figure 3. Estimates of relative selection as a function of topographic slope, forest density, fragmentation index and the distance to natal nest (a proxy of philopatry), encountered by immature red kites during natal dispersal: during the prospecting phase (prospectors, $n = 204$) and during the settlement phase (settlers, $n = 78$). Partial effect reflects how a given habitat is used (> 0) or avoided (< 0) relative to its availability (Avgar et al. 2017, Fieberg et al. 2021). Summaries of the model outputs are provided in the Supporting information.

Figure 4. Immature red kites are spatially less constrained during the prospecting phase (A, $n = 204$ birds) than during the settlement phase (B, $n = 78$ birds). Relative probability of occurrence estimated from habitat selection functions (HSF) predicted over the same prospecting range allowing for comparisons. The available space where the probability of occurrence is predicted was defined by the minimum convex polygons (MCPs) calculated from GPS locations during the prospecting phase for each individual kite-years. Maps of the uncertainty of predictions is provided in the Supporting information.

nonlinearity and controls for habitat availability during two phases of natal dispersal, we demonstrated that habitat selection changed between the prospecting and settlement phases. In general, individuals selected similar habitats between the two phases, but during the settlement phase they were much more responsive to environmental gradients. This shift in habitat selection during the settlement phase resulted in a much more spatially restricted predicted distribution.

During their prospecting phase, immature red kites regularly visited all habitats, even at high elevations (regularly > 1000 m; with $\text{max} = 2800$ m), which is not usually reported for the species (Seoane et al. 2003, Knaus et al. 2018). In contrast, habitats known to be important to breeding adults (i.e. grasslands, arable fields and forests; Hothorn et al. 2011, Heuck et al. 2013) were clearly selected during settlement, but at elevations below 1000 m, while steep topographic slopes were avoided. It is known that many species have reduced fecundity at high elevations (Boyle et al. 2016), which could be due either to unpredictable weather conditions and/or to reduced food availability (Barry 2013, Boyle et al. 2016, Hoorn et al. 2018). In red kites, recent feeding experiments along the elevation gradient suggested that climatic conditions, rather than food availability, are the primary driver of reduced breeding success at higher elevation (Nägeli et al. 2022).

Habitats associated with low human population densities were preferred over those with high densities, although red kites have been shown to benefit from anthropogenic food

provided by households in villages and cities (Orros and Fellowes 2015, Cereghetti et al. 2019) and carcasses in urban areas (Welti et al. 2020). Anthropogenic feeding, however, could explain the selection of urban habitats (cities and villages) at relatively high elevations (> 800 m) during settlement. While the avoidance of high-density areas was stronger for settlers, prospectors were less responsive to it. The habitat selection of settlers associated with low human population densities may be related to the high levels of disturbance and increased risk of mortality typically associated with breeding in highly anthropogenic areas (Boal and Dykstra 2018).

An optimal range of forest density was selected only during the settlement phase, while high landscape heterogeneity was avoided only during this same phase, a finding that aligns with Heuck et al. (2013). Increased heterogeneity, and thus landscape mosaic, may result in a parallel decrease in the quantity, size and accessibility of forest patches (Riitters et al. 2000) that are known to be essential for nesting adult red kites (Hothorn et al. 2011, Heuck et al. 2013, Carter and Powell 2019). Our results therefore suggest that, although arable fields and grasslands were important classes for settlement, so that a mosaic of these habitats should be most beneficial to red kites (Maciorowski et al. 2021), it must be combined with patches of medium-density forest (Hothorn et al. 2011, Heuck et al. 2013, Tomik et al. 2019). Finally, our findings of settlers avoiding steep slopes are consistent with those reported for the species in Spain by Seoane et al. (2003), who suggested that such avoidance

could be a consequence of red kites evading territories of larger raptors that may pose a threat and commonly nest in rugged areas.

The changing patterns of habitat selection along environmental gradients and between dispersal phases can have different non-exclusive underlying causes. First, when immatures first leave the parental home range, they need to gather information as quickly as possible to settle on the most suitable sites. Becoming familiar with habitat available (Delgado et al. 2009, Piper 2011, Lewis et al. 2021) should allow prospecting individuals to settle at the most suitable site available. This learning process may result in clearer habitat preferences during the settlement phase than during the prospecting phase after visiting a wide range of habitats (Piper 2011, Matthysen 2012). Individuals may continue to learn information relevant to foraging and reproduction throughout their lives, with even stronger habitat preferences in later life stages (Kashetsky et al. 2021). However, our results suggest that while age and experience may subtly influence habitat selection, the transitions between dispersal phases exert a stronger influence. Furthermore, habitat selection for settlement could be inherited rather than learned (at least partially, Piper et al. 2013, Nielsen et al. 2013, Dixon et al. 2014) or imprinted prior to the prospecting phase (i.e. 'natal imprinting' sensu Stamps 2001, Mabry and Stamps 2008, Fletcher et al. 2015). Immelman (1975) provides a broader perspective, emphasizing that imprinting and early learning can shape ecological preferences, acting as evolutionary drivers by fostering local adaptations and potentially instigating speciation. The extent to which inheritance, natal imprinting and experience interact to optimize habitat choices made across the lifespan is an emerging area of research and remains to be studied (Nielsen et al. 2013, Dixon et al. 2014, Beardsworth et al. 2021).

A second potential cause for the changes in habitat selection between dispersal phases is that different dispersal phases may also require distinct habitat preferences due to varying resource requirements. Indeed, resource requirements typically differ between activities, implying different habitat requirements and thus different selection rules (Doligez and Boulinier 2008). During foraging, prospectors are not yet constrained to a specific location, which likely allows them to spend most of their time foraging opportunistically, while exploring areas of high elevation and high human density offering favourable food conditions. In contrast, settlers occupying a potential breeding site must consider current but also future resource availability, including steady food supply, nesting sites and breeding conditions, leading to a trade-off between different habitat choices (Doligez and Boulinier 2008, Bonte et al. 2012). Consistent with our results, this shift in resource requirements would therefore suggest that higher elevations, urban areas and heterogeneous environments were avoided from prospecting to settlement, not due to poor foraging opportunities, but likely due to lack of suitable breeding conditions.

Third, competition for suitable habitats with adults and/or newly settled birds could prevent prospecting birds from

using breeding habitats, so they must use less suitable areas when prospecting. This is supported by the very high breeding density in our study area compared to other breeding areas in Europe (Aebischer and Scherler 2021, Nägeli et al. 2022). Therefore, the fact that prospecting individuals were less philopatric and visited areas of high elevation and high human density compared to what is known for breeding adults (in Switzerland and other populations, Hothorn et al. 2011, Heuck et al. 2013, Knaus et al. 2018) could be an indication that the study population is at or near carrying capacity at low elevations. However, in the case of strong competition between settlers and prospectors, we would expect direct exclusion and thus niche segregation between the two dispersal stages rather than increased responsiveness in habitat selection.

Since settlers are more selective and more philopatric, they could be, on the contrary, more constrained by intraspecific competition than prospectors. Indeed, increasing population density due to philopatry is likely to lead to a gradual reduction in the availability of suitable habitats for settlement including nesting sites, especially in dense populations such as in Switzerland. This should force some individuals to settle in low-quality habitats and/or to wait for an empty territory (ideal despotic distribution; Fretwell and Lucas 1969, Sergio and Newton 2003, Hargreaves and Eckert 2014), which may ultimately affect the age at first breeding (Katzenberger et al. 2021, Whitfield et al. 2022). Like other raptors, red kites are indeed known to roost together at night, indicating a potential high importance of social information in this species (Ward and Zahavi 2008), but this could also be the result of individuals waiting for suitable breeding territories to become available, for example by mortality of territory owners (Dwyer et al. 2018).

Our study findings are derived from a highly dense red kite population, which may have influenced the preferences for close distances to natal areas. In such high-density situations, long-distance dispersal could be more prevalent as individuals seek out optimal habitats beyond the saturated local area (Matthysen 2012). In less dense populations, the dynamics of habitat selection and dispersal could be different, with preferences for even closer areas. These potential differences underline the complex interplay between population density, habitat selection and dispersal behaviour. Investigating these dynamics across populations of differing densities represents a promising avenue for future research (Kokko and López-Sepulcre 2006).

Prospectors, being less selective, occupied a broader range of available space than settlers and breeders, thereby buffering the effects of high breeding densities and potentially enhancing immature survival and reproductive success (McLoughlin et al. 2006, Fay et al. 2015, Katzenberger et al. 2021). Like other long-lived species, immature red kites have lower survival rates (Katzenberger et al. 2021), partly due to ontogenescence – declining mortality during development before an increase due to aging (Levitis 2011). This, coupled with exposure to anthropogenic threats during prospecting (De Pascalis et al. 2020), increases risks, particularly as they

use more diverse habitats. Therefore, conservation strategies should consider both natural life-history patterns and human influences on red kite populations.

Depending on the amount of information collected, range of perception, degree of sociality and willingness to move into an empty patch, population expansion should vary between species (Ponchon and Travis 2022). During prospecting, red kites can gather critical information about their environment, potentially at a scale larger than the breeding population, which has therefore the potential to impact their survival and settlement processes, and thus ultimately affects population distribution and dynamics (Kokko and López-Sepulcre 2006, Ponchon et al. 2013, Ponchon and Travis 2022).

Our results thus confirmed that a lack of information about habitat selection processes in different life stages can result in significantly misleading inferences of population distribution and expansion. Indeed, in our case study, investigating only the prospecting phase for habitat modelling would have led to an overestimation of suitable breeding habitats for the population, whereas missing the prospecting phase would have led to an underestimation of suitable areas available but not yet colonized, as well as an underestimation of the habitats used by the entire breeding and non-breeding population. Only by using a longer time series that spans the entire natal dispersal process could we highlight distinct differences in habitat selection between the two dispersal phases. We believe that increased selectivity during settlement occurs in a variety of species and argue that it should be considered when designing conservation measures and when predicting the potential for population expansion, species transfer and/or reintroduction.

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Data availability statement

Data are available from Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8198376> (Orgeret et al. 2023).

Supporting information

The Supporting information associated with this article is available with the online version.

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